

Models for the Inventory Management of Two Merchandise Using the Graded Mean Integration Method of Fuzzy Sets

Paper Id : 19606 Submission Date : 2025-01-10 Acceptance Date : 2025-01-22 Publication Date : 2025-01-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14752632

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Pardeep

Research Scholar
Department Of
Mathematics
D.B.S (PG) College
Dehradun, Uttarakhand,
India

R.K. Pandey

Professor
Department Of
Mathematics
D.B.S (PG) College
Dehradun, Uttarakhand,
India

Abstract This paper explores inventory management issues for two mutually complementary products. The analysis begins by examining these products in a monopoly market and then extends to a perfectly competitive market. Using the concept of fuzzy sets, the paper investigates methods for determining the optimal ordering policy that minimizes total costs. Key findings are presented, along with numerical examples to clarify and illustrate these results. Additionally, the study compares its findings with previous research that did not use fuzzy logic to estimate total costs in a fuzzy context.

Keywords Inventory, Triangular fuzzy number, mutually complementary merchandises, Fuzzy set.

Introduction A fuzzy set is an extension of a classical (or crisp) set in which elements have varying degrees of membership, rather than a binary membership (fully in or fully out). Fuzzy sets were introduced by **Lotfi Zadeh** in 1965 to model and handle uncertainty and imprecision in real-world scenarios where boundaries between categories are not sharply defined.

Membership Function

In fuzzy sets, each element is associated with a membership value ranging between 0 and 1, denoted as $\mu(X)$.

$\mu(x)=1$: Full membership.

$\mu(x)=0$: No membership.

$0 < \mu(x) < 1$: Partial membership.

Representation:

A fuzzy set A in a universe x is represented as:

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) | x \in X\}$$

Where $\mu_A(x)$ is the membership function of A.

A Triangular Fuzzy Number (TFN) is a simple and widely used type of fuzzy number. Its membership function is defined by a triangular shape, characterized by three parameters: the lower limit, the peak (most likely value), and the upper limit.

Definition: A triangular Fuzzy Number is represented as (l,m,u), where:

l: The lower limit where the membership value ($\mu(x)$) is 0.

m: The peak limit or the most representative value where $\mu(x)=1$.

u: The upper limit where the membership value ($\mu(x)$) returns to 0.
The membership function $\mu(x)$ for a triangular fuzzy number is defined as:

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < l \text{ or } x > u \\ \frac{x-l}{m-l}, & l \leq x \leq m \\ \frac{u-x}{u-m}, & m \leq x \leq u \end{cases}$$

2. Graded Mean Integration (GMI) Fuzzy Method for TFN:

The GMI method for TFNs involves taking the mean of the weighted averages of the left and right segments of the triangle, based on their membership grades.

For a TFN (a,b,c), the defuzzified value is calculated as:

$$z^* = \frac{a + 4b + c}{6}$$

Table 1: Comparison of Defuzzification Methods:

Method	Complexity	Precision	Use Case
Centroid	High	High	General-purpose applications
Weighted Average	Moderate	High	Discrete fuzzy sets
Maximum Membership	Low	Low	Simple systems, quick decisions
Graded Mean Integration	Moderate	High	Triangular/trapezoidal fuzzy sets
Bisector	Moderate	Moderate	Symmetrical fuzzy sets

Objective of study

The main objective of the study is:

1. Study fuzzy set theory.
2. Mathematical modeling of the inventory problems for two mutually complementary merchandise.
3. To develop an inventory model with a fuzzy approach.
4. Develop fuzzy mathematical formulation.
5. Derivation of solution of the system under fuzzy approach.
6. Optimize the solution with a graded mean integration method
7. Minimize the total cost.

Review of Literature

The researchers applied the fuzzy sets concept to deal with inventory problems. Zadeh, et al., (1965) developed the fuzzy set theory which is used in several research in different fields like mathematics, and statistics, used in the programming of vehicles and video games, robotics and driverless vehicles, etc. In this article, the fuzzy theory is used in inventory models. With the help of fuzzy numbers, we can control the vagueness of highly fluctuated demand factors. Petrovic and Sweeney [6] fuzzified the demand, lead time, and inventory level into triangular fuzzy numbers in an inventory control model, then decided the order quantity using fuzzy propositions. Chen and Wang [2] fuzzified the ordering cost, inventory cost, and backorder cost into trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and used the functional principle to obtain the estimate of total cost in the fuzzy sense. Vujosevic et al. [14] fuzzified the ordering cost into a trapezoidal fuzzy number in the total cost of an inventory without a backorder model and obtained the fuzzy total cost. Then they did the defuzzification by using centroid and gained the total cost in the fuzzy sense. Gen et al. [3] considered the fuzzy input data expressed by fuzzy numbers, where the interval mean value concept is used to help solve the problem. Roy and Maiti [7] then rewrote the problem of classic economic order quantity into a form of a nonlinear programming problem. They introduced fuzziness both in the objective function and storage area. It was solved by fuzzy both nonlinear and geometric programming techniques for linear membership functions. Ishii and Konno [4] fuzzified the shortage cost into shape fuzzy number in a classical newsboy problem aimed to find an optimal ordering quantity in the sense of fuzzy ordering. Lee and Yao [5] and Yao and Lee [9] proposed the inventory without backorder models in the fuzzy sense, where the order quantity q is fuzzified as the triangular fuzzy number [5] and as the trapezoid fuzzy number [9]. Yao et al. [10] further presented the fuzzy inventory without backorder model in which both the order quantity q and the total demand R are fuzzified as triangular fuzzy numbers. We note that the above papers deal with inventory problems in the fuzzy sense, specifically, for a single merchandise. Rajput et al. (2019) proposed an inventory model with a different type of demand function and discussed the importance of fuzzy parameters in healthcare industries. They used triangular fuzzy number for the demand and defuzzified the model with the signed distance method and get the maximum profit

for all three models. Rajput et al.(2021) presented an EOQ model for deteriorating items under inflation, this article derived a classical and fuzzy model for the effects of deterioration and inflation without any shortage. They used a pentagonal fuzzy number and then optimized the total inventory cost with the GMI defuzzification method.

On the other hand, Yao and Wu [11] discussed the best prices for two mutually complementary merchandise in a monopoly market and a perfect competitive market, such that the total revenue is maximum. However, in [11] the inventory problem of these two merchandise is not taken into account.

This paper addresses the issues of pricing and inventory management for two mutually complementary products within a fuzzy framework, building on the concepts employed in previous studies. Using the concept of fuzzy sets, we explore how to determine the optimal ordering policy for the given inventory problem to minimize total costs. The results are derived, and numerical examples are provided to illustrate the findings. The graded mean integration method is applied to estimate the total cost in the fuzzy sense.

This article is organized as follows. In Section 2, some definitions and properties of fuzzy sets, which will be needed later, are introduced. Section 3 explores the inventory problem for two mutually complementary merchandise. Specifically, in Section 3.1, we consider the crisp case and obtain the optimal order quantities for the merchandise in a monopoly market. In Section 3.2, for a perfectly competitive market, since the prices of two replaceable merchandise may vary a little, so we fuzzify the prices, $P_i, i = 1, 2$, to be the fuzzy numbers and obtain the optimal ordering policies for two merchandise. Section 4 fuzzifies both the order quantities $q_i, i = 1, 2$, and prices $P_i, i = 1, 2$, to be fuzzy numbers, and and defuzzy by the graded mean integration method. Sections 4 and 5 are the result and discussion.

Methodology

Membership Function

In fuzzy sets, each element is associated with a membership value ranging between 0 and 1, denoted as $\mu(X)$.

$\mu(x)=1$: Full membership.

$\mu(x)=0$: No membership.

$0 < \mu(x) < 1$: Partial membership.

Representation:

A fuzzy set A in a universe x is represented as:

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) | x \in X\}$$

Where $\mu_A(x)$ is the membership function of A.

A Triangular Fuzzy Number (TFN) is a simple and widely used type of fuzzy number. Its membership function is defined by a triangular shape, characterized by three parameters: the lower limit, the peak (most likely value), and the upper limit.

Definition: A triangular Fuzzy Number is represented as (l, m, u) , where:

l: The lower limit where the membership value ($\mu(x)$) is 0.

m: The peck limit or the most representative value where $\mu(x)=1$.

$$F(q_1^{(0)}, q_2^{(0)}, x_1^{(0)}, x_2^{(0)}) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{c_i T q_i^{(0)}}{2} + \frac{a_i x_i^{(0)T}}{q_i^{(0)}} \right) = T \sum_{i=1}^2 \sqrt{2a_i c_i x_i^{(0)}} \quad (3.9)$$

3.2. In a perfect competitive market

In a perfectly competitive market, the optimal prices of merchandise X1 and X2 during the planning period T are not always equal to $P_1^{(0)}$ and $P_2^{(0)}$, respectively, but may vary a little. Hence, we shall consider the fuzzy prices instead.

We can fuzzify the price $P_i^{(0)}$ of merchandise X_i as the following triangular fuzzy number.

$$\tilde{P}_i = (P_i^{(0)} - \Delta_{i1}, P_i^{(0)}, P_i^{(0)} + \Delta_{i2})$$

where $0 < \Delta_{i1} < P_i^{(0)}$ and $\Delta_{i2} > 0$.

the fuzzy total cost of two replaceable merchandises X_1 and X_2 with respective fuzzy price \tilde{P}_1 and \tilde{P}_2 , and fuzzy demand \tilde{x}_1 and \tilde{x}_2 , is given by

$$G(q_1, q_2, \tilde{x}_1, \tilde{x}_2) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{c_i T q_i}{2} + \frac{a_i \tilde{x}_i T}{q_i} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

$$G^*(q_1, q_2, x_1, x_2) = (G_1, G_2, G_3) \quad (3.11)$$

$$G_k = \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{c_i T q_i}{2} + \frac{a_i T x_{ik}}{q_i} \right), k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3.12)$$

Therefore, the graded mean integration method of fuzzy number.

$$\begin{aligned} G^*(q_1, q_2) &= \frac{1}{6} (G_1 + 4G_2 + G_3) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i T q_i}{2} + \frac{a_1 T}{6q_1} (x_{11} + 2x_{12} + x_{13}) + \frac{a_2 T}{6q_2} (x_{21} + 2x_{22} + x_{23}) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i T q_i}{2} + \frac{a_1 T}{q_1} x_1^{(0)} + \frac{a_1 T}{6q_1} [a_{11}(\Delta_{11} - \Delta_{12}) + a_{12}(\Delta_{22} - \Delta_{21})] + \frac{a_2 T}{q_2} x_2^{(0)} + \frac{a_2 T}{6q_2} \\ &\quad \times [a_{21}(\Delta_{12} - \Delta_{11}) + a_{22}(\Delta_{21} - \Delta_{22})]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

When $\Delta_{11} = \Delta_{12}$ and $\Delta_{21} = \Delta_{22}$, we have $G^*(q_1, q_2) = F(q_1, q_2, x_1^{(0)}, x_2^{(0)})$, that is, the fuzzy case becomes the crisp case. Our objective in this problem is to determine the optimal values of q_1 and q_2 (denoted by q_1^* and q_2^* , respectively) which minimize $G^*(q_1, q_2)$, for given Δ_{i1} and Δ_{i2} , $i = 1, 2$. For notational convenience, we first define $A_1 = a_{11}(\Delta_{11} - \Delta_{12}) + a_{12}(\Delta_{22} - \Delta_{21})$ and $A_2 = a_{21}(\Delta_{12} - \Delta_{11}) + a_{22}(\Delta_{21} - \Delta_{22})$. Thus, (3.12) can be written as

$$G^*(q_1, q_2) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{c_i T}{2} q_i + \frac{a_i T}{q_i} x_i^{(0)} + \frac{a_i T}{6q_i} A_i \right) \quad (3.13)$$

the necessary conditions for to be minimized $G^*(q_1^*, q_2^*)$ to be minimized are that (q_1^*, q_2^*) satisfy

$$0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial q_1} G^*(q_1, q_2) = \frac{c_1 T}{2} - \frac{a_1 T}{q_1^2} x_1^{(0)} - \frac{a_1 T}{6q_1^2} A_1 \quad (3.14)$$

$$0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial q_2} G^*(q_1, q_2) = \frac{c_2 T}{2} - \frac{a_2 T}{q_2^2} x_2^{(0)} - \frac{a_2 T}{6q_2^2} A_2 \quad (3.15)$$

Simultaneously. By solving (3.14) and (3.15), we obtain

$$q_i^* = \sqrt{\frac{a_i}{3c_i} (6x_i^{(0)} + A_i)}, i = 1, 2 \quad (3.17)$$

Hence (q_1^*, q_2^*) is the optimal solution, and the corresponding minimum total cost in the fuzzy sense is

$$G^*(q_1^*, q_2^*) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{c_i T}{2} q_i^* + \frac{a_i T}{q_i^*} x_i^{(0)} + \frac{a_i T}{6q_i^*} A_i \right) = \frac{T}{3\sqrt{3}} \sum_{i=1}^2 \sqrt{a_i c_i (6x_i^{(0)} + A_i)} \quad (3.18)$$

4. EXAMPLES

The numerical examples provided here demonstrate that the optimal ordering policy as well as the estimate of the total cost in the fuzzy sense can be computed easily using the properties derived in previous sections, specifically, for a firm that sells two mutually complementary merchandise X_1 and X_2 (for example, as described earlier in Section 3, the first-grade sugar and the second-grade sugar).

As in [11], let the monthly demand functions x_1 and x_2 of X_1 and X_2 be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= 30 - 5P_1 + 2P_2 \\ x_2 &= 42 + 3P_1 - 6P_2 \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < P_1 < 6$ and $0 < P_2 < 7$. Also, suppose the values of parameters related to inventory operating as $a_1 = 4, c_1 = 1, a_2 = 3, c_2 = 1, T = 24$.

Example 1. Corresponding to Section 3.1, consider a monopoly market. In this case, the total revenue is

$$\begin{aligned} R(P_1, P_2) &= P_1 x_1 T + P_2 x_2 T = 720P_1 + 1008P_2 + 120P_1 P_2 - 120P_1^2 - 144P_2^2 \\ 0 &< P_1 < 6 \text{ and } 0 < P_2 < 7. \end{aligned}$$

It can be found that the best prices of X_1 and X_2 are $P_1^{(0)} = 6$ and $P_2^{(0)} = 6$, such that $R(6,6) = \max_{P_1, P_2} R(P_1, P_2) = 5184$; and thus, from (3.1) and (3.2), the monthly demand of X_1 and X_2 are $x_1^{(0)} = 12$ and $x_2^{(0)} = 24$, respectively. For the crisp case by equ(3.8) and equ(3.9) we obtain the optimal order quantity $q_1^{(0)} = 9.798$ and $q_2^{(0)} = 12$, and the minimum total cost $F(9.798, 12, 12, 24) = 523.151$.

Example 2. Corresponding to Section 3.2, consider a perfect competitive market, where the prices are fuzzified. Let $\Delta_{12} - \Delta_{11} = 2$ and $\Delta_{22} - \Delta_{21} = 0.8$, where $0 < \Delta_{11} < 6, 0 < \Delta_{21} < 6$, and $\Delta_{i2} > 0, i = 1, 2$. Because $A_1 = a_{11}(\Delta_{11} - \Delta_{12}) + a_{12}(\Delta_{22} - \Delta_{21}) = -8.4$ and $A_2 = a_{21}(\Delta_{12} - \Delta_{11}) + a_{22}(\Delta_{21} - \Delta_{22}) = 1.2$, we have $4x_1^{(0)} + A_1 = 39.6 > 0$ and $4x_2^{(0)} + A_2 = 97.2 > 0$. equ(3.17) and equ(3.18) Then by ,we obtain the optimal order quantity $q_1^* = 9.029, q_2^* = 12.04$, and the minimum total cost in the fuzzy sense $G^*(9.029, 12.04) = 340.137$

The estimate of the total cost in the fuzzy sense by letting $q_{10} = q_1^{(0)} = 9.798$ and $q_{20} = q_2^{(0)} = 12$ (the results obtained in Example 1) The estimate of the total cost in the fuzzy sense by letting $q_{10} = q_1^* = 9.029$ and $q_{20} = q_2^* = 12.04$ (the result obtained in Example 2).

Result and Discussion

Shows that the convex characters of the inventory cost function in both crisp and fuzzy environments. However, the inventory cost is decreased in the fuzzy model. With the help of fuzzy techniques, the inventory cost decreases by almost 4.01% in the fuzzy model compared with the crisp model. After solving this example by the above method using Mathematica software obtained total cost for both environments is obtained below.

Table 2: Optimal Total cost values in different environments with optimal order quantity :

Model	q_1^*	q_2^*	TIC*
Crisp	9.978	12	523.151
Fuzzy	9.029	12.04	340.137

In Table 2, the total cost has a minimum value, the total inventory cost is decreased in the fuzzy model. With the help of fuzzy techniques, the inventory cost decreases by almost 34.9% in the fuzzy model compared with the crisp model.

Convex curve of total inventory cost for crisp model and fuzzy model in the given figures.

Fig 3a. Shows the behavior of total cost in both environments with a time period. Hence total cost is minimal in the fuzzy model.

Fig 3a

Conclusion This paper addresses the pricing and inventory challenges for two mutually complementary products. For products in a monopoly market, we develop a clear total cost function and determine the optimal order quantity by minimizing the total cost. In a perfectly competitive market, we first fuzzify the prices of the two products as fuzzy numbers and then fuzzify the quantities received as fuzzy numbers. In these two fuzzy scenarios, we introduce the graded mean integration method to estimate the total cost in a fuzzy context.

Previous research on single-product inventory models, with or without backorders, has modified these models by fuzzifying the order quantity and total demand quantity. We demonstrate that the result obtained by using the graded mean integration method to denotify the fuzzy number is more accurate than the corresponding crisp value.

References

1. A. Kaufmann, M.M. Gupta, *Introduction to Fuzzy Arithmetic: Theory and Applications*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, 1991.
2. S.-H. Chen, C.-C. Wang, *Backorder fuzzy inventory model under functional principle*, *Information Sciences* 95 (1996) 71-79.
3. M. Gen, Y. Tsujimura, P.Z. Zheng, *An application of fuzzy set theory to inventory control models*, *Computers and Industrial Engineering* 33 (1997) 553-556.
4. H. Ishii, T. Konno, *A stochastic inventory with fuzzy shortage cost*, *European Journal of Operational Research* 106 (1998) 90-94.
5. H.-M. Lee, J.-S. Yao, *Economic order quantity in fuzzy sense for inventory without backorder model*, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 105 (1999) 13-31.
6. D. Petrovic, E. Sweeney, *Fuzzy knowledge-based approach to treating uncertainty in inventory control*, *Computer Integrated Manufacturing Systems* 7 (3) (1994) 147-152.
7. T.K. Roy, M. Maiti, *A fuzzy EOQ model with demand-dependent unit cost under limited storage capacity*, *European Journal of Operational Research* 99 (1997) 425-432.
8. P.-M. Pu, Y.-M. Liu, *Fuzzy topology 1 neighborhood structure of a fuzzy point and Moor-Smith convergence*, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 76 (1980) 571-599.

9. J.-S. Yao, H.-M. Lee, *Fuzzy inventory with or without backorder for fuzzy order quantity with trapezoid fuzzy number*, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 105 (1999) 311-337.
10. J.-S. Yao, S.-C. Chang, J.-S. Su, *Fuzzy inventory without backorder for fuzzy quantity and fuzzy total demand quantity*, *Computers and Operations Research* 27 (2000) 935-962.
11. J.-S. Yao, K. Wu, *The best prices of two mutual complements in the fuzzy sense*, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 111 (2000) 433-454.
12. J.-S. Yao, K. Wu, *Ranking fuzzy numbers based on decomposition principle and signed distance*, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 116 (2000) 275-288.
13. H.J. Zimmermann, *Fuzzy Set Theory and Its Application*, third ed., Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1996.
14. M. Vujosevic, D. Petrovic, R. Petrovic, *EOQ formula when inventory cost is fuzzy*, *International Journal of Production Economics* 45 (1996) 499-504.
15. Rajput N., Chauhan A., and Pandey R.K.: *EOQ model with a discount rate of inflation and optimization with pentagonal fuzzy number* *Int. J. Mathematics in Operational Research*, 20(2), 264-280, (2021).
16. Padiyar S V, Rajput N., Kuraie V C, Padiyar N B., Joshi D., Adhikari M.: *Production Inventory Model with Limited Storage Problem for Perishable Items Under learning Inspection with Fuzzy Parameters* *Design Engineering*, 9, 12821-12839 (2021).
17. Zadeh, L.A.: *Fuzzy sets*. *Inf. Control* 8, 338-356, (1965).
18. Sodhi, M. S., & Tang, C. S. (2021). *Supply chain management for extreme conditions: Research opportunities*. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 57(1), 7-16.